

Impact of Child Pornography and Selfies

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Abstract

Possession and distribution of child pornography is a sex crime that is punishable under both state and federal laws. This crime typically occurs over the Internet or by downloading files from the Internet that contain illegal images. Since files may be mislabelled, or individuals may be directed to Internet sites that they did not intend to visit, claims of possession of child pornography may be incorrectly made against innocent individuals. For this reason, this paper talks about the important to understand the elements of child pornography crimes and defenses.

Introduction

Child pornography is considered to be any depiction of a minor or an individual who appears to be a minor who is engaged in sexual or sexually related conduct. This includes pictures, videos, and computer-generated content. Even altering an image or video so that it appears to be a minor can be considered child pornography.

Definitions of Child Pornography

Since technology moves much faster than the law, crimes committed via social media are often prosecuted by applying existing statutes. Under federal law, child pornography is defined as any visual depiction of sexually explicit conduct involving a minor, which is the standard that would apply to selfies. The U.S. Department of Justice prosecutes child pornography offenses occurring across state or international borders and almost anytime it involves the Internet. Federal charges need not be exclusive as a person could also face criminal liability under state child pornography laws, which are largely similar to, and sometimes more comprehensive than, federal laws. Many states further define elements of the crime, such as what constitutes sexually explicit conduct or who is considered a minor. For example:

- Massachusetts extends its child pornography laws to include participating, with lascivious intent, in the depiction of a nude minor in any visual material.
- In South Carolina, the judge or jury may infer that the participants in alleged child pornography are minors based on the material’s title or text.
- Utah’s definition of “sexually explicit content” includes actual or simulated “explicit representation of defecation or urination functions.”

Child Pornography and Selfies: When Children Can Commit the Crime

If an adult takes a sexually explicit picture of a minor and shares it via social media or text message, that adult will likely have run afoul of child pornography laws. But what about a minor who takes selfies and sends them discreetly to another teen? What if the receiver then forwards the photos to others? Have they violated any laws? In many states, the answer is yes.

Though their laws were created to protect minors from exploitation caused by others, states are prosecuting minors under child pornography statutes for sending nude or otherwise lurid self-portraits, even when the minors sent the selfies without coercion. The common quirk in the laws is that there is no exception for taking or distributing sexually explicit pictures of oneself. Thus, a high school student sending a racy selfie to a boyfriend or girlfriend could subject both themselves and the receiver to prosecution for child pornography. If the picture makes its way around other social circles through online or direct sharing, anyone who received or distributed the photo could also find themselves open to charges.

Direction of Future Laws

The overall trend on both the federal and state levels is toward broader definitions of child pornography with increased prosecutions and harsher penalties for those connected to it. One of the gray areas in the age of social media is what constitutes “possession” of child pornography. Most social media sites can now store large caches of images indefinitely on the Internet, lessening the need for viewers to download files to their computers. Other services, such as Snapchat, can be used to distribute selfies that auto-delete themselves after a few seconds (though the receiver may take a screen shot before the image disappears).

Since merely viewing child pornography is illegal in many states, browsing a website or knowingly receiving illegal images would be criminal activity in those jurisdictions. Other states’ child pornography laws, however, have “possession” requirements that are somewhat archaic in the digital age. States have since taken steps to close such loopholes and expand the reach of their child pornography laws to include developing and future technologies, but this is an area of law that is rapidly evolving to meet the times. For teens sending or exchanging risqué pictures, their concern can no longer be limited to whether it may bring embarrassment or even parental and academic discipline. Instead, they need also to consider whether that sexually explicit selfie can get them prosecuted under child pornography laws.

Effects of Child Pornography

The effect of child portrayed is vast majority of children who appear in child pornography have not been abducted or physically forced to participate. In most cases they know the producer it may even be their father and are manipulated into taking part by more subtle means. Nevertheless, to be the subject of child pornography can have devastating physical, social, and psychological effects on children.

The abuse was taking place, victims described the physical pain (e.g., around the genitals), accompanying somatic symptoms (such as headaches, loss of appetite, and sleeplessness), and feelings of psychological distress (emotional isolation, anxiety, and fear). However, most also felt a pressure to cooperate with the offender and not to disclose the offense, both out of loyalty to the offender and a sense of shame about their own behavior.

The Internet and Other Forms of Child Sexual Abuse

In addition to child pornography, the Internet facilitates child sexual abuse in the following ways:

- It allows networking among child abuse perpetrators. The Internet facilitates a subculture of pedophiles, who may share information and tactics and support each other’s belief systems.
- It may be used to seek out and groom victims. Perpetrators may enter children or teens chat rooms under an assumed identity to access and establish relationships with potential victims.
- It may be used in cyber-stalking. Children may be sexually harassed via the Internet.
- It may be used to promote child sexual tourism. Information is made available to help individuals locate child-sex tourism operators or to make direct contact with child prostitutes.
- It may be used in trafficking children. Mail-order children are available over the Internet.

Kinds of Child Pornography

Here are some examples of the different kinds of child pornography:

- visual representation (that is, a photo, film, video or another image) of a minor taking part in a clearly sexual activity
- visual representation of certain parts of a minor’s body for a sexual purpose
- encouraging, showing (for example in a photo, film, video or another image) or describing a sexual activity with a minor that is forbidden
- Child pornography can be in different forms, for example, in pictures, videos, written material or sound recordings.

Punishment for Child Pornography

- Anyone who makes, prints, publishes, makes available, sells, imports, exports or advertises child pornography, or has child pornography to make it public, can be sent to prison for up to 14 years. The minimum punishment is 1 year in prison.
- Anyone who has, looks up or gets (accesses) child pornography can be sent to prison for up to 10 years. The minimum punishment is six months in prison.

Conclusion

It’s important to realize that people close to your children can be a greater threat than strangers. Follow your instincts - if someone who has access to your children makes you uncomfortable, end that relationship. Also, tell your children to never allow anyone to touch them in a way that makes them feel scared, uncomfortable or confused. Parents can provide the information and support for children to grow-up able to have loving and healthy relationships. Help them see that pornography use doesn’t offer them the practice, insight or pathway they need toward loving, caring connections.

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